

LEARNING TRAINER AIDS FOR KOREAN LANGUAGE

Kyaw Zin Aung
Student, 5th Year, B.C.Sc.
University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Supervised By
Dr. Win Lai Hnin
Faculty of Computer Science
University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Abstract. This system is an innovative educational platform designed to provide a comprehensive and dealing in learning experience across various types, with a particular focus on the Korean language and culture. This application serves a wide collection of educational tools to cater to different learning styles and goals, making it suitable for both casual learners and those preparing for academic or professional advancement. At the core of this system lies a suite of interactive video lessons, designed to show up complex topics by breaking them down into easily digestible segments. This approach adds to user comprehension and retention, fostering a deeper understanding of the material.

Keyword: educational tools, quiz, video lessons, learning experience

INTRODUCTION

In addition to these core features, this system consists of specialized notes for the Test of Proficiency in Korean (TOPIK), providing targeted preparation materials that are essential for the TOPIK exam. The application also enlarges beyond basic instruction, offering advanced lessons that examine into suggestion topics, whether in language, culture, or other educational fields. This makes a resourceful tool that adapts to the evolving needs of its users, providing a dynamic and flexible learning environment. By integrating these diverse educational resources, this system stands out as an ideal choice for anyone serious about learning, whether for personal enrichment, academic purposes, or professional development. The application's holistic approach assures that learners not only acquire knowledge but also develop a deep understanding of the subject matter, making it a valuable companion in the journey of lifelong learning.

PROBLEM

The application also supplies to those with specific academic goals, particularly through its specialized notes for the Test of Proficiency in Korean (TOPIK). These targeted materials are indispensable for users, aiming to excel in the exam, offering focused preparation and valuable insights. Moreover, this system goes beyond the basics by providing advanced lessons that explore intricate topics across language, culture, and other educational domains. This accomplished ensures that the platform progresses with the learner, serving a dynamic and adaptable learning environment. Through the harmonized of these comprehensive educational resources, this system itself as the premier choice for learners of all kinds—whether they are seeking personal enrichment.

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

www.ucsh.edu.mm

APPROACH

In the system under consideration, the workflow is distinctly divided between administrators and users, each with specific roles and responsibilities. Administrators are required to log in to gain access to functionalities of the system. Once authenticated, they have the authority to manage various aspects of the platform, including adding new users, quiz questions, story scripts, vocabulary, and lesson videos. Administrators are also responsible for reviewing user-submitted payment screenshots and quiz attempt data. Additionally, they oversee the updating and deletion of user information, quiz content, story materials, vocabulary, and lesson videos, ensuring the content of the system remains current and accurate.

Users, on the other hand, must register and log in to access the platform's features. Upon successful login, users can immediately begin learning the Basic Course without requiring approval from the administrators. They can also edit their profiles, attempt quizzes, explore the story section, study the TOPIK guide, and access additional lessons. However, to gain access to more advanced content, such as the Intermediate and Advanced Courses, and to obtain certificates, users must first receive approval from the administrators.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes [1]. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are eight tables in this application. The tables are Register, Rating, Record, Quiz, Payment images, Vocabulary, Lesson Video, Story. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The Internet has become a critical resource in modern life, elevating the significance of education systems beyond traditional onsite training. Education systems now encompass a broad range of opportunities, from expanding access to knowledge to fostering comparative selection among students. For educational management, this system creates new avenues for learning and innovation, while students benefit from the ability to make informed choices quickly. Just as a well-designed interior can influence one's perception of a space, an effective educational system must offer intuitive navigation, seamless data retrieval, and prompt feedback to ensure user engagement [2].

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

This project is a comprehensive educational application designed to facilitate learning the Korean language. It is a versatile platform accessible on any device with a browser. The application offers a wide range of features, including video lessons, quizzes, cultural stories, vocabulary, grammar notes, and additional learning resources. With a user-friendly interface and an engaging user experience, this system ensures effective language acquisition without the need for email accounts, as it operates solely with phone numbers.

REFERENCES

- [1] CodingZest, Firebase Realtime database, <https://youtube/miJooBq9iwE>, 2022
- [2] Tim, Color Theory, <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/3769762/web-colors-in-an-android-color-xml-resource-file>, February, 2016
- [3] Seemile, Lesson videos Reference, <https://youtube/qqPhAlxv0iY>, 2010
- [4] Let's Learn Korea, Quiz Reference, <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsNiKYtRPuEA8ibtzNVzig>, 2022